

A Study of Algebraic Curves in Neutrosophic Real Ring $R(I)$ by Using the One-Dimensional Geometric AH-Isometry

Safwan Owera¹, Malath F ALaswad²

¹ Faculty of Science, Dept. of Mathematical Statistics, University of Aleppo, Aleppo, Syria

² Faculty of Science, Dept. of Mathematical Statistics, University of Aleppo, Aleppo, Syria, e-mail: malaz.aswad@yahoo.com;

Abstract: The objective of this paper is to study and define some algebraic curves with neutrosophic variables in neutrosophic real field $R(I)$, where we study what are the relationships between classical algebraic curves and neutrosophic algebraic curves depending on the geometric isometry (AH-Isometry).

Keywords: Neutrosophic real ring $R(I)$, AH-isometry, Neutrosophic algebraic curves.

Introduction

Algebraic Geometry is one of the branches of algebra that deals with the study of geometric shapes through familiar algebraic concepts and theories [1]. There were several approaches to geometry, all of which are usually classified as algebraic geometry, at the end of the nineteenth century. Lazare Carnot (1753-1823) attributed to algebraic geometry which is about algebraic curves and their intersection with the sides of a triangle [2], but this concept developed a lot in the second half of the nineteenth century.

Neutrosophy is a new branch of philosophy concerns with the indeterminacy in all areas of life and science. It has become a useful tool in generalizing many classical systems such as equations [30], number theory [3], and linear spaces [4,5], and ring of matrices [19-31].

Recently, Abobala, and Hatip have presented the concept of one-dimensional AH-isometry to study the correspondence between neutrosophic plane $R(I)$ and the classical module $R \times R$.

In this work, we use the one-dimensional AH-isometry to turn the general case of algebraic curves in real ring $R(I)$ with one variable into two classical algebraic curves so we will go from $R(I)$ space into $R \times R$ space, we study the properties of our algebraic curves then we go back to $R(I)$ space using AH-isometry.

Neutrosophic Functions on $R(I)$.

Definition:

Let $R(I) = \{a + bI; a, b \in R\}$ where $I^2 = I$ be the neutrosophic field of reals. The one-dimensional isometry (AH-Isometry) is defined as follows: [49]

$$\begin{aligned} T: R(I) &\rightarrow R \times R \\ T(a + bI) &= (a, a + b) \end{aligned}$$

Definition:

Let $f: R(I) \rightarrow R(I); f = f(X)$ and $X = x + yI \in R(I)$ the f is called a neutrosophic real function with one neutrosophic variable.

Example:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Take } f: R(I) \rightarrow R(I); f(X) &= X^2 + IX + 2I = (x + yI)^2 + I(x + yI) + 2I \\ &= x^2 + I(y^2 + 2xy + x + y + 2) \end{aligned}$$

Theorem:

Let $f: R(I) \rightarrow R(I)$ be a neutrosophic real function with one variable, $X = x + yI \in R(I)$ then f can be turned into two classical real functions.

Computing Powers in $R(I)$.

To compute such equation: $(a + bI)^{c+dI}; a, b, c, d \in R$ we need the one-dimensional isometry again:

$$T[(a + bI)^{c+dI}] = (a, a + b)^{(c, c+d)} = (a^c, (a + b)^{c+d}),$$

Which means

$$\begin{aligned} (a + bI)^{c+dI} &= T^{-1}(a^c, (a + b)^{c+d}), \\ &= a^c + I[(a + b)^{c+d} - a^c]. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem:

Let $R(I)$ be the neutrosophic field of reals, we have:

1. $\sin(a + bI) = \sin a + I[\sin(a + b) - \sin a]$
2. $\cos(a + bI) = \cos a + I[\cos(a + b) - \cos a]$
3. $e^{x+Iy} = e^x + I(e^{x+y} - e^x)$

Algebraic Curves In Neutrosophic Real Ring $R(I)$:**Definition : Neutrosophic Strophoide.**

Let $Y = y_1 + y_2I, X = x_1 + x_2I, A = a_1 + a_2I \in R(I), a_1, a_2, x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2 \in \mathbf{R}$, then we define a neutrosophic strophoide as follows:

$$Y^2 = X^2 \cdot \frac{A + X}{A - X} ; A > 0$$

This equation can be written as follows:

$$(y_1 + y_2I)^2 = (x_1 + x_2I)^2 \cdot \frac{(a_1 + a_2I) + (x_1 + x_2I)}{(a_1 + a_2I) - (x_1 + x_2I)} ; a_1 + a_2I > 0$$

Theorem :

Let $Y = y_1 + y_2I, X = x_1 + x_2I, A = a_1 + a_2I \in R(I)$, then if $A = a_1 + a_2I$ is invertible, the neutrosophic strophoide $(y_1 + y_2I)^2 = (x_1 + x_2I)^2 \cdot \frac{(a_1+a_2I)+(x_1+x_2I)}{(a_1+a_2I)-(x_1+x_2I)}$ is equivalent to the direct product of two classical strophoide.

Proof. Consider the equation $(y_1 + y_2I)^2 = (x_1 + x_2I)^2 \cdot \frac{(a_1+a_2I)+(x_1+x_2I)}{(a_1+a_2I)-(x_1+x_2I)}$

Now, we have:

$$y_1^2 + (y_2^2 + 2y_1y_2)I = [x_1^2 + (x_2^2 + 2x_1x_2)I] \cdot \frac{(a_1 + x_1) + (a_2 + x_2)I}{(a_1 - x_1) + (a_2 - x_2)I}$$

$$\begin{aligned} y_1^2 + (y_2^2 + 2y_1y_2)I &= [x_1^2 + (x_2^2 + 2x_1x_2)I] \cdot \left[\frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{(a_1 - x_1)(a_2 + x_2) - (a_1 + x_1)(a_2 - x_2)}{(a_1 - x_1)[(a_1 + a_2) - (x_1 + x_2)]} I \right] \end{aligned}$$

by computing its direct image with AH-isometry, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} T(y_1^2 + (y_2^2 + 2y_1y_2)I) \\ = T(x_1^2 + (x_2^2 + 2x_1x_2)I)T\left(\frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)}\right) \\ + \frac{(a_1 - x_1)(a_2 + x_2) - (a_1 + x_1)(a_2 - x_2)}{(a_1 - x_1)[(a_1 + a_2) - (x_1 + x_2)]} I \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (y_1^2, y_1^2 + y_2^2 + 2y_1y_2) \\ = (x_1^2, x_1^2 + x_2^2 + 2x_1x_2) \cdot \left(\frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)}, \frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)} \right) \\ + \frac{(a_1 - x_1)(a_2 + x_2) - (a_1 + x_1)(a_2 - x_2)}{(a_1 - x_1)[(a_1 + a_2) - (x_1 + x_2)]} \end{aligned}$$

Then.

$$(y_1^2, (y_1 + y_2)^2) = (x_1^2, (x_1 + x_2)^2) \cdot \left(\frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)}, \frac{(a_1 + x_1)[(a_1 + a_2) - (x_1 + x_2)] + (a_1 - x_1)(a_2 + x_2) - (a_1 + x_1)(a_2 - x_2)}{(a_1 - x_1)[(a_1 + a_2) - (x_1 + x_2)]} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned} (y_1^2, (y_1 + y_2)^2) \\ = (x_1^2, (x_1 + x_2)^2) \cdot \left(\frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)}, \frac{(a_1 + x_1)[(a_1 + a_2) - (x_1 + x_2)] + (a_1 - x_1)(a_2 + x_2) - (a_1 + x_1)(a_2 - x_2)}{(a_1 - x_1)[(a_1 + a_2) - (x_1 + x_2)]} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$(y_1^2, (y_1 + y_2)^2) = (x_1^2, (x_1 + x_2)^2) \cdot \left(\frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)}, \frac{(a_1 + x_1)[(a_1 - x_1)] + (a_1 - x_1)(a_2 + x_2)}{(a_1 - x_1)[(a_1 + a_2) - (x_1 + x_2)]} \right)$$

$$(y_1^2, (y_1 + y_2)^2) = (x_1^2, (x_1 + x_2)^2) \cdot \left(\frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)}, \frac{(a_1 - x_1)(a_1 + x_1 + a_2 + x_2)}{(a_1 + x_1)[(a_1 + a_2) - (x_1 + x_2)]} \right)$$

$$(y_1^2, (y_1 + y_2)^2) = (x_1^2, (x_1 + x_2)^2) \cdot \left(\frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)}, \frac{(a_1 + a_2) + (x_1 + x_2)}{(a_1 + a_2) - (x_1 + x_2)} \right)$$

$$(y_1^2, (y_1 + y_2)^2) = \left(x_1^2 \frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)}, (x_1 + x_2)^2 \frac{(a_1 + a_2) + (x_1 + x_2)}{(a_1 + a_2) - (x_1 + x_2)} \right)$$

So that we have:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Gamma_1: y_1^2 = x_1^2 \frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)}; a_1 > 0 \\ \Gamma_2: (y_1 + y_2)^2 = (x_1 + x_2)^2 \frac{(a_1 + a_2) + (x_1 + x_2)}{(a_1 + a_2) - (x_1 + x_2)}; (a_1 + a_2) > 0 \end{array} \right.$$

Remark :

If $a_1 + a_2I$ is invertible, we can write the equation of neutrosophic strophoide as follows:

$$(y_1 + y_2I)^2 = (x_1 + x_2I)^2 \cdot \frac{(a_1 + a_2I) + (x_1 + x_2I)}{(a_1 + a_2I) - (x_1 + x_2I)}.$$

Now, we should discuss the cases of non-invertible of $a_1 + a_2I$.

$a_1 + a_2I$ is not invertible, then we have cases:

1- $a_1 = 0, a_1 + a_2 \neq 0$, this means that the neutrosophic strophoide will be equivalent

to direct product of classical strophoide $(y_1 + y_2)^2 = (x_1 +$

$x_2)^2 \frac{(a_1 + a_2) + (x_1 + x_2)}{(a_1 + a_2) - (x_1 + x_2)}; (a_1 + a_2) > 0$ with classical image two line $\begin{cases} y_1 = i x_1 \\ y_1 = -i x_1 \end{cases}$.

2- $a_1 \neq 0, a_1 + a_2 = 0$, this implies that the neutrosophic strophoide will be

equivalent to direct product of classical strophoide $y_1^2 = x_1^2 \frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)}; a_1 > 0$ with

classical image two line $\begin{cases} y_1 = i (x_1 + x_2) \\ y_1 = -i (x_1 + x_2) \end{cases}$.

3- If $a_1 = 0, a_1 + a_2 = 0$, this implies that the neutrosophic strophoide will be

equivalent to direct product of classical image two line $\begin{cases} y_1 = i x_1 \\ y_1 = -i x_1 \end{cases}$ with classical

image two line $\begin{cases} y_1 = i (x_1 + x_2) \\ y_1 = -i (x_1 + x_2) \end{cases}$.

Theorem:

Let Γ_1, Γ_2 are two classical strophoide, then the direct product of Γ_1, Γ_2 is equivalent to the neutrosophic strophoide Γ .

Proof.

Let Γ_1, Γ_2 are two classical strophoide, where:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Gamma_1: y_1^2 = x_1^2 \cdot \frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)}; a_1 > 0 \\ \Gamma_2: y_2^2 = x_2^2 \cdot \frac{(a_2 + x_2)}{(a_2 - x_2)}; a_2 > 0 \end{array} \right.$$

Now, we take the inverse image of the AH-isometry, we have:

$$T^{-1}(y_1^2, y_2^2) = T^{-1}(x_1^2, x_2^2) \cdot T^{-1}\left(\frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)}, \frac{(a_2 + x_2)}{(a_2 - x_2)}\right)$$

$$y_1^2 + (y_2^2 - y_1^2)I = [x_1^2 + (x_2^2 - x_1^2)I] \cdot \left[\frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)} + \left(\frac{(a_2 + x_2)}{(a_2 - x_2)} - \frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)} \right) I \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned} y_1^2 + (y_2^2 - y_1^2)I &= [x_1^2 + (x_2^2 - x_1^2)I] \cdot \left[\frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \left(\frac{(a_2 + x_2)(a_1 - x_1) - (a_2 - x_2)(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)(a_2 - x_2)} \right) I \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$y_1^2 + (y_2^2 - y_1^2)I = [x_1^2 + (x_2^2 - x_1^2)I] \cdot \left[\frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)} + \left(\frac{(a_2 + x_2)}{(a_2 - x_2)} - \frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)} \right) I \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned} y_1^2 + (y_2^2 - y_1^2)I &= [x_1^2 + (x_2^2 - x_1^2)I] \cdot \left[\frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \left(\frac{(a_2 + x_2)}{(a_2 - x_2)} - \frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)} + \frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_2 - x_2)} - \frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_2 - x_2)} \right) I \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} y_1^2 + (y_2^2 - y_1^2)I &= [x_1^2 + (x_2^2 - x_1^2)I] \cdot \left[\frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \left(\left\{ \frac{(a_2 + x_2)}{(a_2 - x_2)} - \frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_2 - x_2)} \right\} + \left\{ -\frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)} + \frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_2 - x_2)} \right\} \right) I \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} y_1^2 + (y_2^2 - y_1^2)I &= [x_1^2 + (x_2^2 - x_1^2)I] \cdot \left[\frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \left\{ \frac{(a_2 + x_2) - (a_1 + x_1)}{(a_2 - x_2)} - \frac{(a_1 + x_1)(a_2 - x_2) - (a_1 + x_1)(a_1 - x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)(a_2 - x_2)} \right\} I \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& y_1^2 + (y_2^2 - y_1^2)I \\
&= [x_1^2 + (x_2^2 - x_1^2)I] \cdot \left[\frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)} \right. \\
& \left. + \frac{(a_1 - x_1)[(a_2 + x_2) - (a_1 + x_1)] - (a_1 + x_1)(a_2 - x_2) - (a_1 + x_1)(a_1 - x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)(a_2 - x_2)} I \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$y_1^2 + (y_2^2 - y_1^2)I = [x_1^2 + (x_2^2 - x_1^2)I].$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left[\frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)} + \frac{(a_1 - x_1)[(a_2 + x_2) - (a_1 + x_1)] - (a_1 + x_1)[(a_2 - x_2) - (a_1 - x_1)]}{(a_1 - x_1)(a_2 - x_2)} I \right] \frac{(a_1 + x_1)}{(a_1 - x_1)} \\
& + \frac{(a_1 - x_1)[(a_2 + x_2) - (a_1 + x_1)] - (a_1 + x_1)[(a_2 - x_2) - (a_1 - x_1)]}{(a_1 - x_1)(a_2 - x_2)} I \\
&= \frac{(a_1 + x_1) + [(a_2 + x_2) - (a_1 + x_1)]I}{(a_1 - x_1) + [(a_2 - x_2) - (a_1 - x_1)]I}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
y_1^2 + (y_2^2 - y_1^2)I &= [x_1^2 + (x_2^2 - x_1^2)I] \cdot \left[\frac{(a_1 + x_1) + [(a_2 + x_2) - (a_1 + x_1)]I}{(a_1 - x_1) + [(a_2 - x_2) - (a_1 - x_1)]I} \right] \\
y_1^2 + (y_2^2 - y_1^2)I &= [x_1^2 + (x_2^2 - x_1^2)I] \cdot \left[\frac{a_1 + (a_2 - a_1)I + [x_1 + (x_2 - x_1)I]}{a_1 + (a_2 - a_1)I - [x_1 + (x_2 - x_1)I]} \right] \dots (*)
\end{aligned}$$

We let $X = x_1 + (x_2 - x_1)I$, $Y = y_1 + (y_2 - y_1)I$, $A = a_1 + (a_2 - a_1)$, then we can prove that:

$$Y^2 = y_1^2 + (y_2^2 - y_1^2)I, X^2 = x_1^2 + (x_2^2 - x_1^2)$$

Then the equation (*) can be written as follows:

$$\Gamma: Y^2 = X^2 \cdot \frac{A + X}{A - X}; A > 0$$

This equation is a neutrosophic strophoide Γ .

Example:

Let the equation by a neutrosophic strophoide:

$$\Gamma: (y_1 + y_2 I)^2 = (x_1 + x_2 I)^2 \cdot \frac{(4 - 2I) + (x_1 + x_2 I)}{(4 - 2I) - (x_1 + x_2 I)}$$

Then, its equation be equivalent to direct product of two classical strophoide:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Gamma_1: y_1^2 = x_1^2 \left(\frac{4 + x_1}{4 - x_1} \right) \\ \Gamma_2: (y_1 + y_2)^2 = (x_1 + x_2)^2 \left(\frac{2 + x_1}{2 - x_1} \right) \end{array} \right.$$

Example:

Let Γ_1, Γ_2 are two classical strophoide, where:

$$\begin{cases} \Gamma_1: y_1^2 = x_1^2 \left(\frac{1+x_1}{2} \right) \\ \Gamma_2: y_2^2 = x_2^2 \left(\frac{2+x_2}{2-x_2} \right) \end{cases}$$

Then by theorem 6.4 we have.

$$\Gamma: Y^2 = X^2 \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{3}{2}I\right) + X}{\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{3}{2}I\right) - X}$$

.Definition: Neutrosophic Cycloide.

Let $Y = y_1 + y_2I, X = x_1 + x_2I, R = r_1 + r_2I, t = t_1 + t_2I \in$

$\mathbf{R}(I), r_1, r_2, t_1, t_2, x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2 \in \mathbf{R}$, then we define a neutrosophic Cycloide as follows:

$$X = \mathbf{R}(1 - \sin t), Y = \mathbf{R}(1 - \cos t)$$

This equation can be written as follows:

$$x_1 + x_2I = (r_1 + r_2I)(1 - \sin(t_1 + t_2I)), y_1 + y_2I = (r_1 + r_2I)(1 - \cos(t_1 + t_2I))$$

Theorem:

Let $Y = y_1 + y_2I, X = x_1 + x_2I, R = r_1 + r_2I, t = t_1 + t_2I \in \mathbf{R}(I)$, then if $r_1 + r_2I$ is invertible, the neutrosophic Cycloide $X = \mathbf{R}(1 - \sin t), Y = \mathbf{R}(1 - \cos t)$ is equivalent to the direct product of two classical Cycloide.

Proof. Consider the equation $X = \mathbf{R}(1 - \sin t), Y = \mathbf{R}(1 - \cos t)$

Now, we have:

$$x_1 + x_2I = (r_1 + r_2I) \left(1 - \sin(t_1) - I(\sin(t_1 + t_2) - \sin(t_1)) \right)$$

$$y_1 + y_2I = (r_1 + r_2I) \left(1 - \cos(t_1) - I(\cos(t_1 + t_2) - \cos(t_1)) \right)$$

by computing its direct image with AH-isometry, we get:

$$T(x_1 + x_2I) = T(r_1 + r_2I).T(1 - \sin(t_1) - I[\sin(t_1 + t_2) - \sin(t_1)])$$

$$(x_1, x_1 + x_2) = (r_1, r_1 + r_2) \cdot (1 - \sin(t_1), 1 - \sin(t_1 + t_2))$$

$$(x_1, x_1 + x_2) = (r_1(1 - \sin(t_1)), (r_1 + r_2)(1 - \sin(t_1 + t_2)))$$

Then.

$$\begin{cases} x_1 = r_1(1 - \sin(t_1)) \\ x_1 + x_2 = (r_1 + r_2)(1 - \sin(t_1 + t_2)) \end{cases}$$

By a similar, we have.

$$\begin{cases} y_1 = r_1(1 - \cos(t_1)) \\ y_1 + y_2 = (r_1 + r_2)(1 - \cos(t_1 + t_2)) \end{cases}$$

So that we have:

$$\begin{cases} \Gamma_1: x_1 = r_1(1 - \sin(t_1)), y_1 = r_1(1 - \cos(t_1)) \\ \Gamma_2: x_1 + x_2 = (r_1 + r_2)(1 - \sin(t_1 + t_2)), y_1 + y_2 = (r_1 + r_2)(1 - \cos(t_1 + t_2)) \end{cases}$$

Remark:

If $r_1 + r_2I$ is invertible, we can write the equation of neutrosophic cycloide as follows:

$$X = R(1 - \sin t) , Y = R(1 - \cos t).$$

Now, we should discuss the cases of non-invertible of $r_1 + r_2I$.

The $r_1 + r_2I$ is not invertible, then we have two cases:

- 1- $r_1 = 0, r_1 + r_2 \neq 0$, this means that the neutrosophic cycloide will be equivalent to direct product of classical cycloide $x_1 + x_2 = (r_1 + r_2)(1 - \sin(t_1 + t_2)), y_1 + y_2 = (r_1 + r_2)(1 - \cos(t_1 + t_2))$ with the origin point $(0,0)$.
- 2- $r_1 \neq 0, r_1 + r_2 = 0$, this means that the neutrosophic cycloide will be equivalent to direct product of classical cycloide $x_1 = r_1(1 - \sin(t_1)), y_1 = r_1(1 - \cos(t_1))$ with the origin point $(0,0)$.
- 3- If $r_1 = 0, r_1 + r_2 = 0$, this implies that the neutrosophic cycloide will be equivalent to the origin point $(0,0)$.

Theorem:

Let Γ_1, Γ_2 are two classical cycloide, then the direct product of Γ_1, Γ_2 is equivalent to the neutrosophic cycloide Γ .

Proof.

Let Γ_1, Γ_2 are two classical cycloide, where:

$$\begin{cases} \Gamma_1: x_1 = r_1(1 - \sin t_1), y_1 = r_1(1 - \cos t_1) \\ \Gamma_2: x_2 = r_2(1 - \sin t_2), y_2 = r_2(1 - \cos t_2) \end{cases}$$

Now, we take the inverse image of the AH-isometry, we have:

$$T^{-1}(x_1, x_2) = T^{-1}(r_1, r_2).T^{-1}((1 - \sin t_1), (1 - \sin t_2))$$

$$x_1 + (x_2 - x_1)I = [r_1 + (r_2 - r_1)I]. [1 - \sin t_1 + ((1 - \sin t_2) - (1 - \sin t_1))I]$$

$$x_1 + (x_2 - x_1)I = [r_1 + (r_2 - r_1)I]. [1 - \sin t_1 + (1 - \sin t_2 - 1 + \sin t_1)I]$$

$$x_1 + (x_2 - x_1)I = [r_1 + (r_2 - r_1)I]. [1 - \sin t_1 - (\sin t_2 - \sin t_1)I]$$

$$x_1 + (x_2 - x_1)I = [r_1 + (r_2 - r_1)I]. [1 - (\sin t_1 + (\sin t_2 - \sin t_1))I]$$

$$x_1 + (x_2 - x_1)I = [r_1 + (r_2 - r_1)I]. [1 - (\sin t_1 + (\sin(t_2 - t_1 + t_1) - \sin t_1))I]$$

We let $X = x_1 + (x_2 - x_1)I, R = r_1 + (r_2 - r_1)I, t = t_1 + (t_2 - t_1)I$, then we can prove that:

$$\sin t = \sin[t_1 + (t_2 - t_1)I] = \sin t_1 + (\sin(t_2 - t_1 + t_1) - \sin t_1)I$$

Then, we have.

$$X = R. (1 - \sin t)$$

Now, by the same argument, we have.

$$Y = R. (1 - \cos t)$$

So.

$$\Gamma: \begin{cases} X = R. (1 - \sin t) \\ Y = R. (1 - \cos t) \end{cases}$$

This equation is a neutrosophic cycloid Γ .

Example:

Let the equation by a neutrosophic cycloide:

$$\begin{cases} x_1 + x_2I = (3 - 2I). [1 - \sin(t_1 + t_2I)] \\ y_1 + y_2I = (3 - 2I). [1 - \cos(t_1 + t_2I)] \end{cases}$$

Then, its equation be equivalent to direct product of two classical cycloide:

$$\begin{cases} \Gamma_1: x_1 = 3(1 - \sin t_1), y_1 = 3(1 - \cos t_1) \\ \Gamma_2: x_1 + x_2 = 1 - \sin(t_1 + t_2), y_1 + y_2 = 1 - \cos(t_1 + t_2) \end{cases}$$

Example:

Let Γ_1, Γ_2 are two classical cycloide, where:

$$\begin{cases} \Gamma_1: x_1 = 2(1 - \sin t_1), y_1 = 2(1 - \cos t_1) \\ \Gamma_2: x_2 = 5(1 - \sin t_2), y_2 = 5(1 - \cos t_2) \end{cases}$$

$$\Gamma: \begin{cases} X = (2 + 3I)(1 - \sin t) \\ Y = (2 + 3I)(1 - \cos t) \end{cases}$$

Definition: Neutrosophic Cardioide.

Let $\rho = \rho_1 + \rho_2 I, \theta = \theta_1 + \theta_2 I \in R(I), \rho_1, \rho_2, \theta_1, \theta_2 \in R$, then we define a neutrosophic Cardioide as follows:

$$\rho = (1 + \cos \theta)$$

This equation can be written as follows:

$$\rho_1 + \rho_2 I = (1 + \cos \theta_1) + [\cos(\theta_1 + \theta_2) - \cos \theta_1] I$$

Theorem:

Let $\rho = \rho_1 + \rho_2 I, \theta = \theta_1 + \theta_2 I \in R(I)$, then if $\theta_1 + \theta_2 I$ is invertible, the neutrosophic Cardioide

$\rho = (1 + \cos \theta)$ is equivalent to the direct product of two classical Cardioide.

Proof. Consider the equation $\rho = (1 + \cos \theta)$

Now, we have:

$$\rho_1 + \rho_2 I = (1 + \cos \theta_1) + [\cos(\theta_1 + \theta_2) - \cos \theta_1] I$$

by computing its direct image with AH-isometry, we get:

$$T(\rho_1 + \rho_2 I) = T((1 + \cos \theta_1) + [\cos(\theta_1 + \theta_2) - \cos \theta_1] I)$$

$$(T\rho_1, T\rho_1 + T\rho_2) = (1 + \cos \theta_1, 1 + \cos(\theta_1 + \theta_2))$$

Then.

$$\begin{cases} T\rho_1 = 1 + \cos \theta_1 \\ T\rho_1 + T\rho_2 = 1 + \cos(\theta_1 + \theta_2) \end{cases}$$

So that we have:

$$\begin{cases} \Gamma_1: \rho_1 = 1 + \cos\theta_1 \\ \Gamma_2: \rho_1 + \rho_2 = 1 + \cos(\theta_1 + \theta_2) \end{cases}$$

Remark:

If $\theta_1 + \theta_2 I$ is invertible, we can write the equation of neutrosophic Cardioide as follows:

$$\rho = (1 + \cos\theta).$$

Now, we should discuss the cases of non-invertible of $\theta_1 + \theta_2 I$.

The $\theta_1 + \theta_2 I$ is not invertible, then we have two cases:

- 1- $\theta_1 = 0, \theta_1 + \theta_2 \neq 0$, this means that the neutrosophic Cardioide will be equivalent to direct product of classical Cardioide $(\rho_1 + \rho_2) = 1 + \cos(\theta_1 + \theta_2)$ with the classical circle $\rho_1 = 2$.
- 2- $\theta_1 \neq 0, \theta_1 + \theta_2 = 0$, this means that the neutrosophic Cardioide will be equivalent to direct product of classical Cardioide $\rho_1 = 1 + \cos(\theta_1)$ with the classical circle $(\rho_1 + \rho_2) = 2$.
- 3- If $\theta_1 = 0, \theta_1 + \theta_2 = 0$ this means that the neutrosophic Cardioide will be equivalent to direct product of classical circle $(\rho_1 + \rho_2) = 2$ with the classical circle $\rho_1 = 2$.

Theorem:

Let Γ_1, Γ_2 are two classical Cardioide, then the direct product of Γ_1, Γ_2 is equivalent to the neutrosophic Cardioide Γ .

Proof.

Let Γ_1, Γ_2 are two classical Cardioide, where:

$$\begin{cases} \Gamma_1: \rho_1 = 1 + \cos\theta_1 \\ \Gamma_2: \rho_2 = 1 + \cos\theta_2 \end{cases}$$

Now, we take the inverse image of the AH-isometry, we have:

$$T^{-1}(\rho_1, \rho_2) = T^{-1}(1 + \cos\theta_1, 1 + \cos\theta_2)$$

$$\rho_1 + (\rho_2 - \rho_1)I = [1 + \cos\theta_1 + (1 + \cos\theta_2 - (1 + \cos\theta_1))I]$$

$$\rho_1 + (\rho_2 - \rho_1)I = [1 + \cos\theta_1 + (\cos\theta_2 - \cos\theta_1)I]$$

$$\rho_1 + (\rho_2 - \rho_1)I = 1 + [\cos\theta_1 + (\cos(\theta_1 + [\theta_2 - \theta_1]) - \cos\theta_1)I]$$

We let $\rho = \rho_1 + (\rho_2 - \rho_1)I, \theta = \theta_1 + (\theta_2 - \theta_1)I$, then we can prove that:

$$\cos\theta = \cos(\theta_1 + [\theta_2 - \theta_1]I) = \cos\theta_1 + (\cos(\theta_1 + [\theta_2 - \theta_1]) - \cos\theta_1)I$$

Then, we have.

$$\rho_1 + (\rho_2 - \rho_1)I = 1 + \cos(\theta_1 + [\theta_2 - \theta_1]I)$$

So.

$$\Gamma: \rho = 1 + \cos\theta$$

This equation is a neutrosophic Cardioide Γ .

Example:

Let the equation by a neutrosophic Cardioide:

$$\rho_1 + \rho_2 I = 1 + \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{4}I\right)$$

Then, its equation be equivalent to direct product of two classical Cardioide:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Gamma_1: \rho_1 = 1 + \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3}\right) \\ \Gamma_2: \rho_1 + \rho_2 = 1 + \cos\left(\frac{7\pi}{12}\right) \end{array} \right.$$

Example:

Let Γ_1, Γ_2 are two classical Cardioide, where:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Gamma_1: \rho_1 = 1 + \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) \\ \Gamma_2: \rho_2 = 1 + \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) \end{array} \right.$$

$$\Gamma: \left\{ \rho = 1 + \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{\pi}{4}I\right) \right.$$

Conclusions

In this paper we have studied some concepts of neutrosophic real analysis depending on the one-dimensional AH-isometry. We have provided a strict definition of some algebraic curves in neutrosophic real ring $\mathbf{R}(I)$, and we study the properties of this curves, and we

proved some theorems for this curves, also, we find relationships between a classical algebraic curves and neutrosophic algebraic curves.

References

1. R.HARTSHORNE, "Algebraic Geometry", California, 1997.
2. S.IITAKA, "Algebraic Geometry", New York, 1981.
3. Hodge, W.V.D., Pedoe, Daniel "Method of Algebraic Geometry", Vol. 1, Cambridge University, 1994.
4. Abobala, M., "A Study of AH-Substructures in n -Refined Neutrosophic Vector Spaces", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science", Vol. 9, pp.74-85. 2020.
5. Sankari, H., and Abobala, M., "Neutrosophic Linear Diophantine Equations With two Variables", Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol. 38, pp. 22-30, 2020.
6. Smarandache, F., " A Unifying Field in Logics: Neutrosophic Logic, Neutrosophy, Neutrosophic Set, Neutrosophic Probability", American Research Press. Rehoboth, 2003.
7. Olgun, N., and Hatip, A., "The Effect Of The Neutrosophic Logic On The Decision Making, in Quadruple Neutrosophic Theory And Applications", Belgium, EU, Pons Editions Brussels, pp. 238-253. 2020.
8. Abobala, M., "Classical Homomorphisms Between n -refined Neutrosophic Rings", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science", Vol. 7, pp. 74-78. 2020.
9. Smarandache, F., and Abobala, M., n -Refined neutrosophic Rings, International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 5 , pp. 83-90, 2020.
10. Abobala, M., On Some Special Substructures of Neutrosophic Rings and Their Properties, International Journal of Neutrosophic Science", Vol. 4 , pp. 72-81, 2020.
11. Abobala, M., "On Some Special Substructures of Refined Neutrosophic Rings", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 5, pp. 59-66. 2020.

12. Smarandache, F., and Kandasamy, V.W.B., " Finite Neutrosophic Complex Numbers", Source: arXiv. 2011.
13. Agboola, A.A.A., Akwu, A.D., and Oyebo, Y.T., " Neutrosophic Groups and Subgroups", International J. Math. Combin, Vol. 3, pp. 1-9. 2012.
14. Smarandache, F., " n -Valued Refined Neutrosophic Logic and Its Applications in Physics", Progress in Physics, 143-146, Vol. 4, 2013.
15. Adeleke, E.O., Agboola, A.A.A., and Smarandache, F., " Refined Neutrosophic Rings I", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 2(2), pp. 77-81. 2020.
16. Hatip, A., and Abobala, M., " AH-Substructures In Strong Refined Neutrosophic Modules", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 9, pp. 110-116 . 2020.
17. Smarandache F., and Abobala, M., " n -Refined Neutrosophic Vector Spaces", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 7, pp. 47-54. 2020.
18. Adeleke, E.O., Agboola, A.A.A., and Smarandache, F., " Refined Neutrosophic Rings II", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 2(2), pp. 89-94. 2020.
19. Abobala, M., " On Refined Neutrosophic Matrices and Their Applications In Refined Neutrosophic Algebraic Equations", Journal Of Mathematics, Hindawi, 2021
20. Abobala, M., " A Study Of Nil Ideals and Kothe's Conjecture In Neutrosophic Rings", International Journal of Mathematics and Mathematical Sciences, hindawi, 2021
21. Abobala, M., " Semi Homomorphisms and Algebraic Relations Between Strong Refined Neutrosophic Modules and Strong Neutrosophic Modules", Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol. 39, 2021.
22. Giorgio, N, Mehmood, A., and Broumi, S., " Single Valued neutrosophic Filter", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 6, 2020.
23. Abobala, M., " On The Characterization of Maximal and Minimal Ideals In Several Neutrosophic Rings", Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol. 45, 2021.

-
24. Milles, S, Barakat, M, and Latrech, A., " Completeness and Compactness In Standard Single Valued neutrosophic Metric Spaces", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol.12 , 2021.
 25. Abobala, M., "Neutrosophic Real Inner Product Spaces", Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol. 43, 2021.
 26. Abobala, M., On The Representation of Neutrosophic Matrices by Neutrosophic Linear Transformations, Journal of Mathematics, Hindawi, 2021.
 27. Merkepci, H., and Abobala, M., " On The Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Rings", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, 2023.
 28. Sarkis, M., " On The Solutions Of Fermat's Diophantine Equation In 3-refined Neutrosophic Ring of Integers", Neoma Journal of Mathematics and Computer Science, 2023.
 29. Hatip, A., "An Introduction To Weak Fuzzy Complex Numbers ", Galoitica Journal Of Mathematical Structures and Applications, Vol.3, 2023.
 30. Merkepci, H., and Ahmad, K., " On The Conditions Of Imperfect Neutrosophic Duplets and Imperfect Neutrosophic Triplets", Galoitica Journal Of Mathematical Structures And Applications, Vol.2, 2022.
 31. Von Shtawzen, O., " Conjectures For Invertible Diophantine Equations Of 3-Cyclic and 4-Cyclic Refined Integers", Journal Of Neutrosophic And Fuzzy Systems, Vol.3, 2022.
 32. Abobala, M., and Zeina, M.B., " A Study Of Neutrosophic Real Analysis By Using One Dimensional Geometric AH-Isometry", Galoitica Journal Of Mathematical Structures And Applications, Vol.3, 2023.

Received: December 23, 2022. **Accepted:** April 01, 2023